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PHALOTRIS LEMNISCATUS (Dumeril's Diadem Snake). PREDATION.

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172:726–732) and foot autotomy (Hoso 2012. Proc. R. Soc. B Biol. Sci. 279: 4811–4816). Five to ten percent of wild *S. c. caliginosa* have regenerated feet, whereas almost none of the other subspecies of *S. caliginosa* (e.g., *S. c. picta*) from an island free from snake predation did (Hoso 2012, *op. cit.*). Thus, our observation provides additional support that *S. c. caliginosa* is potentially a major prey for *P. iwasakii*.

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PHALOTRIS LEMNISCATUS (Dumeril's Diadem Snake). PRE-DATION. *Phalotris lemniscatus* is a small snake that occurs in open habitats in southern Brazil, Argentina, and Uruguay (Schaefer 1998. Herpetol. Rev. 29:178). It has semi-fossorial habits, sheltering under litter, rocks, or trunks (Entiauspe-Neto et al. 2016. Check List 12:1964). Individuals are aposematically colored, with a uniform reddish dorsum and frequently with longitudinal black dorsal strips (Ferrarezzi 1993. Mem. Inst. Butantan 55:21–38). Here we describe for the first time a predation event on *P. lemniscatus*.

On 10 October 2017 at 1935 h, in the city of Nova Petrópolis, state of Rio Grande do Sul, southern Brazil (29.3624°S, 51.1100°W; WGS 84), we observed a Burrowing Owl (*Athene cunicularia*) on the ground holding a *P. lemniscatus* in its talons. The owl was on an unpaved road surrounded by native forest. Upon our approach, the owl flew away and abandoned the snake, which was still alive. When handling the snake we observed no signs of lacerations, suggesting that we observed the initial phase of the predation event. Identification was made through detailed examination of the animal, as well as by using photographic vouchers (Fig. 1). There are numerous records of Burrowing Owl predation on snakes, including *Phalotris mertensi* (Cruz et al. 2014. Herpetol. Bull. 128:26–27). Our observation is relevant due to the aposematic coloration of *P. lemniscatus*, which in this case was not effective at preventing capture by an owl.

FIG. 1. *Phalotris lemniscatus* observed during a predation event by a Burrowing Owl (*Athene cunicularia*).

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PHILODRYAS PATAGONIENSIS (Green Racer). DIET. *Philodryas patagoniensis* is a medium-sized terrestrial colubrid, which inhabits open areas of South America (Hartmann and Marques 2005. Amphibia-Reptilia 26:25–31; Carreira and Maneyro 2013. Guía de Reptiles del Uruguay. Ediciones de la Fuga, Montevideo. 283 pp.). It is considered a generalist predator of small animals such as rodents, birds, fish, amphibians, and snakes (López and Giraud 2008. J. Herpetol. 42:474–480; Zanella and Cechin 2009. Iheringia. Sér. Zool. 99:111–114), including conspecifics (Pontes et al. 2003. Herpetol. Rev. 34:154).

At 1200 h on 2 November 2017, in a temporary pond in the Estação Ecológica do Taim, Rio Grande do Sul state, Brazil (32.53764°S, 52.53787°W, WGS 84; 7 m elev.) an adult *P. patagoniensis* was observed in the final phase of ingestion of a Swamp Eel, *Synbranchus marmoratus*. Only the tail of the eel was protruding from the snake's mouth, indicating that the ingestion began at the head (Fig. 1). To my knowledge, this is the first case of predation of *S. marmoratus* by *P. patagoniensis*.

I am thankful to Liliانا Essi for photographing this event and sharing the photo with me.

FIG. 1. Adult *Philodryas patagoniensis* eating a Swamp Eel, *Synbranchus marmoratus*.

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PHILODRYAS VIRIDISSIMA (Common Green Racer). DIET. Many snakes exhibit an ontogenetic shift in diet (Shine and Wall 2007. In Reilly et al. [eds.], Lizard Ecology: The Evolutionary Consequences of Foraging Mode, pp. 173–208. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK). Canopy-dwelling snakes, such as *Philodryas viridissima*, shift from eating mainly frog and lizard prey to small mammals during their life (Martins and Oliveira 1999. Herpetol. Nat. Hist. 6:78–150). Here, we report prey of two individuals of *P. viridissima* of different ages.

At 1531 h on 13 January 2013, we found an adult male *P. viridissima* (total length = 105.5 cm; tail length = 27.7 cm; voucher: INPA – H 32336) swallowing a relatively large male *Guerlinguetus aestuans* (Brazilian Squirrel; total length = 31.02